

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Numerical methods for solving the Neumann problem for the wave equation

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Keywords: Lyapunov function, hyperbolic system, difference scheme, mixed problem, numerical solution **Abstract** This paper investigates the numerical solution of the Neumann boundary value problem for the one-dimensional wave equation. In addition, the study focuses on transforming the classical second-order wave equation into a system of first-order symmetric hyperbolic equations and applying appropriate boundary and initial conditions. Using the method of Riemann invariants, is reduced to a canonical form suitable for numerical treatment. A difference scheme is constructed to approximate the solution, and its stability is analyzed through the Lyapunov functional method. Conditions ensuring exponential stability of the numerical scheme are derived. Numerical experiments demonstrate the accuracy and stability of the proposed approach, confirming the theoretical results.

Introduction

Neumann problems are applied to the wave propagation equation and to the management of processes associated with wave propagation, especially the control of gas or oil pressure in pipelines. The existence of solutions to differential problems of this type has been investigated in [1]-[3], and their numerical solutions were analyzed in [4]-[6]. In this article, we attempt to apply Lyapunov stability theory to the numerical solution of Neumann problems for one-dimensional hyperbolic systems. In particular, we study the problem of constructing and analyzing a difference scheme for the numerical computation of stable solutions to the Neumann problem for a one-dimensional linear symmetric t -hyperbolic system. The main idea of this research is to investigate the Lyapunov stability of solutions to mixed problems for one-dimensional hyperbolic systems by constructing a Lyapunov function and obtaining a priori estimates in functional spaces

Formulation of the problem.

$$u_{tt} = a^2 u_{xx}, \quad 0 \leq x \leq l, \quad t > 0 \quad (1)$$

$$u(0, x) = \varphi(x), \quad u_t(0, x) = \psi(x) \quad (2)$$

$$u_x(t, 0) = \gamma_1 u_t(t, 0), \quad u_x(t, l) = -\gamma_2 u_t(t, l) \quad (3)$$

here,

$$a_1, \gamma_1, \gamma_2 > 0$$

are real numbers.

The main objective of this study is to investigate the numerical solution of the Neumann problem associated with the wave propagation equation. The problem is reformulated as a system of two first-order partial differential equations.

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \begin{pmatrix} w_1(t, x) \\ w_2(t, x) \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -a^2 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \begin{pmatrix} w_1(t, x) \\ w_2(t, x) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$$at, t = 0 \quad w_1(0, x) = \varphi(x), \quad w_2(0, x) = \psi_x(x) \quad (5)$$

initial conditions at $x = 0$ and $x = l$,

$$w_2(t, 0) = \gamma_1 w_1(t, 0), \quad w_2(t, l) = -\gamma_2 w_1(t, l) \quad (6)$$

We have obtained a mixed problem posed for the symmetric t-hyperbolic system of equations (4)-(6) that satisfies the boundary conditions. Now, in this problem, we make the following substitution to bring it into canonical form:

$$\begin{pmatrix} w_1(t, x) \\ w_2(t, x) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -a & a \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} u_1(t, x) \\ u_2(t, x) \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

and

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \begin{pmatrix} u_1(t, x) \\ u_2(t, x) \end{pmatrix} + \mathbf{K} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \begin{pmatrix} u_1(t, x) \\ u_2(t, x) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

here

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & -a \end{pmatrix}.$$

The initial conditions with respect to Riemann invariants are:

$$u_1(0, x) = \Phi(x) \triangleq \Delta = \triangleq \frac{1}{2} \varphi_x(x) - \frac{1}{2a} \psi(x), \quad u_2(0, x) = \Psi(x) \triangleq \frac{1}{2a} \psi(x) - \frac{1}{2} \varphi_x(x) \quad (9)$$

and

$$u_1(t, 0) = -\frac{1 - \gamma_1 a}{1 + \gamma_1 a} u_2(t, 0), \quad u_2(t, l) = \frac{1 - \gamma_2 a}{1 + \gamma_2 a} u_1(t, l). \quad (10)$$

boundary conditions are written in this form. Let the initial data

$$\varphi(x), \psi(x) \in W_2^1((0, l), R^n)$$

satisfy the compatibility condition:

$$\begin{cases} a\varphi_x(0) = \psi(0), & x = 0, t = 0, \\ a\gamma_2\varphi_x(l) = -\psi(l), & x = l, t = 0, \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

here $W_2^1((0, l), R^n)$ is the Sobolev space. Lyapunov function

$$L(t) = \int_0^l (\mu(x) \cdot U(t, x), U(t, x)) dx \quad (12)$$

we get in sight. Here

$$\mu(x) = \begin{pmatrix} e^{-vx}\mu_1 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{vx}\mu_2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad U(t, x) = \begin{pmatrix} u_1(t, x) \\ u_2(t, x) \end{pmatrix}.$$

become a matrix, v , μ_1 , μ_2 - positive numbers. In this work, the exponential stagnation of the mixed problem (8)-(10) are studied and a difference scheme is built as numerical solution. Also, the convergence scheme is proved and the results of a numerical experiment are presented.

Theorem(Exponential stability). System (8) with boundary conditions (10) is exponentially stable in the L^2 , if there exists such $\nu > 0$ and $\mu_i > 0$, $i = 1, 2$ that the following matrices

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & a \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} e^{-\nu l}\mu_1 & 0 \\ 0 & \mu_2 \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} 0 & r \\ s & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & a \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mu_1 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{\nu l}\mu_2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & s \\ r & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (13)$$

are positive definite.

Proof. We calculate the derivative of the Lyapunov function:

$$\begin{aligned} L'(t) &= \int_0^l \partial_t(\mu(x)U, U) dx = \int_0^l (\mu(x)\partial_t U, U) dx + \int_0^l (\mu(x)U, \partial_t U) dx \\ &= \int_0^l (\mu(x)(-\mathbf{K}\partial_x U), U) dx + \int_0^l (\mu(x)U, (-\mathbf{K}\partial_x U)) dx \\ &= - \int_0^l [(\mu(x)\mathbf{K}\partial_x U, U) + (\mu(x)U, \mathbf{K}\partial_x U)] dx. \end{aligned}$$

since $\mu'(x)K = -\nu|K|\mu(x)$ and $(\mu(x)K\partial_x U, U) = \partial_x(\mu(x)KU, U) - (\mu'(x)KU, U)$, we have the following identity:

$$L'(t) = - \int_0^l \partial_x(\mu(x)\mathbf{K}U, U) dx - \int_0^l (\nu|\mathbf{K}|\mu(x)U, U) dx = -(\mathbf{K}\mu(x)U, U)\Big|_0^l - \int_0^l (\nu|\mathbf{K}|\mu(x)U, U) dx,$$

where

$$|\mathbf{K}| = \begin{bmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & a \end{bmatrix}.$$

Transform separately the each term of the penultimate obtained identity:

$$\begin{aligned}
-(K\mu(x)U, U)\Big|_0^l &= -\left[(K\mu(l)U(t, l), U(t, l)) - (K\mu(0)U(t, 0), U(t, 0))\right] \\
&= -\left(\begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & -a \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} e^{-vl}\mu_1 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{vl}\mu_2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_1(t, l) \\ u_2(t, l) \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} u_1(t, l) \\ u_2(t, l) \end{bmatrix}\right) \\
&\quad + \left(\begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & -a \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mu_1 & 0 \\ 0 & \mu_2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_1(t, 0) \\ u_2(t, 0) \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} u_1(t, 0) \\ u_2(t, 0) \end{bmatrix}\right) \\
&= -\left(\begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & a \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} e^{-vl}\mu_1 & 0 \\ 0 & \mu_2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_1(t, l) \\ u_2(t, 0) \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} u_1(t, l) \\ u_2(t, 0) \end{bmatrix}\right) \\
&\quad + \left(\begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & a \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mu_1 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{vl}\mu_2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_1(t, 0) \\ u_2(t, l) \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} u_1(t, 0) \\ u_2(t, l) \end{bmatrix}\right) \\
&= -\left(\begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & a \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} e^{-vl}\mu_1 & 0 \\ 0 & \mu_2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_1(t, l) \\ u_2(t, 0) \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} u_1(t, l) \\ u_2(t, 0) \end{bmatrix}\right) \\
&\quad + \left(\begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & a \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mu_1 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{vl}\mu_2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & s \\ r & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_1(t, l) \\ u_2(t, 0) \end{bmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & s \\ r & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_1(t, l) \\ u_2(t, 0) \end{bmatrix}\right) \\
&= -\left(\begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & a \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} e^{-vl}\mu_1 & 0 \\ 0 & \mu_2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_1(t, l) \\ u_2(t, 0) \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} u_1(t, l) \\ u_2(t, 0) \end{bmatrix}\right) \\
&\quad + \left(\begin{pmatrix} as & 0 \\ 0 & ar \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mu_1 s & 0 \\ 0 & e^{vl}\mu_2 r \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_1(t, l) \\ u_2(t, 0) \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} u_1(t, l) \\ u_2(t, l) \end{bmatrix}\right) < 0
\end{aligned}$$

Taking these transformations into account, we obtain

$$L'(t) = -(\mathbf{K}\mu(x)U, U)\Big|_0^l - \int_0^l ([\nu|\mathbf{K}|\mu(x)]U, U) dx < 0.$$

If we choose large enough, then the inequality holds

$$([\nu|\mathbf{K}|\mu(x)]U, U) > a(\mu(x)U, U)$$

Then we have $L'(t) < -\alpha L(t)$. Hence,

$$L(t) \leq e^{-\alpha t} L(0), \quad t > 0.$$

However, since there is such a constant $\gamma > 0$, such that

$$\frac{1}{\gamma} \|U(t, \cdot)\|_{L^2((0, l), R^n)}^2 \leq L(t) \leq \gamma \|U(t, \cdot)\|_{L^2((0, l), R^n)}^2$$

we obtain

$$\|U(t, \cdot)\|_{L^2((0, l), R^n)} \leq \gamma e^{-\nu t/2} \left\| \begin{pmatrix} \varphi \\ \psi \end{pmatrix} \right\|_{L^2((0, l), R^n)}, \quad t \in [0, +\infty).$$

The differefce scheme

We take the equidistant grid:

$$t_n = n\Delta t, \quad n = \overline{0, N}, \quad N\Delta t = T, \quad x_{j-\frac{1}{2}} = j\Delta x,$$

$$x_j = \left(j + \frac{1}{2}\right) \Delta x, \quad M\Delta x = l, \quad j = \overline{0, M-1},$$

$$U_j^n = \frac{1}{\Delta x} \int_{x_{j-\frac{1}{2}}}^{x_{j+\frac{1}{2}}} U(t^n, x) dx, \quad j = \overline{0, M-1}$$

We consider the following mixed problem for the one-dimensional hyperbolic system (8)-(10) and integrate (8) over the interval $\left[x_{j-\frac{1}{2}}, x_{j+\frac{1}{2}}\right]$

$$\partial_t \int_{x_{j-\frac{1}{2}}}^{x_{j+\frac{1}{2}}} U(t, x) dx = \mathbf{K} \left(U \left(t, x_{j-\frac{1}{2}} \right) - U \left(t, x_{j+\frac{1}{2}} \right) \right) \quad j = \overline{0, M-1}. \quad (14)$$

We integrate the resulting equality over t on the interval $[t_n, t_{n+1}]$:

$$\int_{x_{j-\frac{1}{2}}}^{x_{j+\frac{1}{2}}} U(t_{n+1}, x) dx - \int_{x_{j-\frac{1}{2}}}^{x_{j+\frac{1}{2}}} U(t_n, x) dx = \mathbf{K} \left(\int_{t_n}^{t_{n+1}} U(t, x_{j-\frac{1}{2}}) dt - \int_{t_n}^{t_{n+1}} U(t, x_{j+\frac{1}{2}}) dt \right) \quad (15)$$

$$j = \overline{1..M-1}$$

or

$$U_j^{n+1} = U_j^n - \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x} \mathbf{K} \left(U_{j+\frac{1}{2}}^n - U_{j-\frac{1}{2}}^n \right) \quad (16)$$

$$j = \overline{0, M-1}, \quad n = \overline{0, N-1}$$

Let us assume that the KFL condition is satisfied $a \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x} \leq 1$

$$\begin{bmatrix} (u_1)_j^{n+1} \\ (u_2)_j^{n+1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} (u_1)_j^n \\ (u_2)_j^n \end{bmatrix} - a \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x} \begin{bmatrix} (u_1)_j^n - (u_1)_{j-1}^n \\ (u_2)_j^n - (u_2)_{j+1}^n \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

$$j = \overline{0, M-1}, \quad n = \overline{0, N-1}.$$

The initial conditions (9) are approximated exactly

$$(u_1)_j^0 = \frac{1}{\Delta x} \int_{x_{j-\frac{1}{2}}}^{x_{j+\frac{1}{2}}} \Phi(x) dx, \quad (u_2)_j^0 = \frac{1}{\Delta x} \int_{x_{j-\frac{1}{2}}}^{x_{j+\frac{1}{2}}} \Psi(x) dx, \quad (18)$$

$$j = \overline{0..M-1}$$

The boundary conditions are approximated as follows

$$\begin{pmatrix} (u_1)_{-1}^{n+1} \\ (u_2)_M^{n+1} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & s \\ r & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} (u_1)_{M-1}^{n+1} \\ (u_2)_0^{n+1} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (19)$$

Definition. The difference scheme (17) with the difference boundary condition (19) is exponentially stable if there exist constants $\eta > 0$ and $C > 0$ such that, for any initial condition,

$$U_j^0 \in L^2((x_{j-\frac{1}{2}}, x_{j+\frac{1}{2}}), \mathbb{R}^n)$$

the solution of the difference boundary value problem (17)-(19) satisfies the inequality

$$\Delta x \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} (U_j^n, U_j^n) \leq e^{-\eta t_n} \Delta x \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} (U_j^0, U_j^0),$$

$$n = \overline{1, N}.$$

As a discrete Lyapunov function we propose

$$L^n = \Delta x \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} (U_j^n, \mu_j U_j^n), \quad \mu_j = \mu(x_j), \quad (20)$$

$$j = \overline{1..M-1}$$

Theorem. Let $T > 0$ and be a discrete Lyapunov function defined by formula (20). If the CFL condition is satisfied $a \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x} \leq 1$ and there exist real numbers $\nu > 0$ and $\mu_i > 0$, $i = 1, 2$ such that $0 < a(1 - e^{-\nu \Delta x}) < 1$ and

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mu_1 a e^{-\nu x_M} & 0 \\ 0 & \mu_2 a e^{\nu x_{-1}} \end{bmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} 0 & r \\ s & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mu_1 a e^{-\nu x_0} & 0 \\ 0 & \mu_2 a e^{\nu x_{M-1}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & s \\ r & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

positive definite matrix, then the numerical solution

$$U_j^n = \begin{pmatrix} (u_1)_j^n \\ (u_2)_j^n \end{pmatrix}$$

of the difference boundary value problem (17)-(19) is exponentially stable for the norm L^2 the norm.

Proof. Let us introduce the following notation $[W_j^n = \begin{bmatrix} (u)_{j-1}^n \\ (v)_{j+1}^n \end{bmatrix}$, $\mathbf{D} = \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x} |\mathbf{K}|$. Taking these notations into account, we calculate the difference ratio for the discrete Lyapunov function: 1).

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{L^{n+1} - L^n}{\Delta t} &= \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} [(U_j^{n+1}, \mu_j U_j^{n+1}) - (U_j^n, \mu_j U_j^n)] \\ &= \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} [(\{U_j^n - \mathbf{D} [U_j^n - W_j^n]\}, \mu_j \{U_j^n - \mathbf{D} [U_j^n - W_j^n]\}) \\ &- \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} (U_j^n, \mu_j U_j^n)] = \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} [(U_j^n, \mu_j U_j^n) - (U_j^n, \mu_j U_j^n)] - \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} [2(\mu_j U_j^n, \mathbf{D} [U_j^n - W_j^n])]; \end{aligned}$$

2).

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} (\mu_j \mathbf{D} [U_j^n - W_j^n], \mathbf{D} [U_j^n - W_j^n]) \\
&= \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} (\mu_j \mathbf{D} [U_j^n - W_j^n], \mathbf{D} [U_j^n - W_j^n]) - \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} 2 (\mu_j U_j^n, \mathbf{D} [U_j^n - W_j^n]) = \\
&= \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} [(\mu_j \mathbf{D} U_j^n, \mathbf{D} U_j^n) \\
&- \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} (\mu_j \mathbf{D} W_j^n, \mathbf{D} W_j^n) - 2 (\mu_j \mathbf{D} U_j^n, \mathbf{D} W_j^n) - 2 (\mu_j U_j^n, \mathbf{D} U_j^n) + 2 (\mu_j U_j^n, \mathbf{D} W_j^n) \\
&= \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} [(\mu_j \mathbf{D} U_j^n, \mathbf{D} U_j^n)] + 2 (\mu_j (\mathbf{E} - \mathbf{D}) U_j^n, \mathbf{D} W_j^n) + \\
&+ \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} (\mu_j \mathbf{D} W_j^n, \mathbf{D} W_j^n) - 2 (\mu_j U_j^n, \mathbf{D} U_j^n)
\end{aligned}$$

By virtue of the CFL condition, the matrix $(\mathbf{E} - \mathbf{D}) \geq 0$ and $(\mathbf{E} - \mathbf{D})\mu_j \mathbf{D}$ - a positive definite diagonal matrix. Taking into account the boundary conditions

$$\begin{pmatrix} (u_1)_{-1}^{n+1} \\ (u_2)_J^{n+1} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & s \\ r & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} (u_1)_{M-1}^{n+1} \\ (u_2)_0^{n+1} \end{pmatrix}$$

we will receive

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} (\mu_j W_j^n, \mathbf{D} W_j^n) = e^{-\nu \Delta x} \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} (U_j^n, \mu_j |\mathbf{K}| U_j^n) + \\
&+ \left(\begin{pmatrix} r (u_1)_{M-1}^{n+1} \\ s (u_2)_0^{n+1} \end{pmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} \mu^+ e^{-\nu x_0} a \cdot s & 0 \\ 0 & \mu^- e^{\nu x_{M-1}} a \cdot r \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} (u_1)_{M-1}^{n+1} \\ (u_2)_0^{n+1} \end{pmatrix} \right) \\
&- \left(\begin{bmatrix} (u_1)_{M-1}^n \\ (u_2)_0^n \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} \mu^+ e^{-\nu x_M} a & 0 \\ 0 & \mu^- e^{\nu x_{-1}} a \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} (u_1)_{M-1}^n \\ (u_2)_0^n \end{bmatrix} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

Let us assume that the dissipativity condition is satisfied

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mu^+ a e^{-\nu x_M} & 0 \\ 0 & \mu^- a e^{\nu x_{-1}} \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} \mu^+ e^{-\nu x_0} a \cdot s^2 & 0 \\ 0 & \mu^- e^{\nu x_{M-1}} a \cdot r^2 \end{bmatrix} > 0$$

Then we have

$$\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} (\mu_j W_j^n, \mathbf{D} W_j^n) \leq e^{-\nu \Delta x} \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} (U_j^n, \mu_j |\mathbf{K}| U_j^n)$$

and therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{L^{n+1} - L^n}{\Delta t} &\leq e^{-\nu\Delta t} \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} (U_j^n, \mu_j | KU_j^n) - \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} (U_j^n, \mu_j | KU_j^n) = \\ &= (e^{-\nu\Delta t} - 1) \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} (U_j^n, \mu_j | KU_j^n) \leq 0 \end{aligned}$$

Here $\eta = a(1 - e^{-\nu\Delta x})$. Let $0 < \eta < 1$. Then

$$\frac{L^{n+1} - L^n}{\Delta t} \leq -\eta L^n.$$

Recursively applying this inequality we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} L^{n+1} &< (1 - \Delta t\eta)^{n+1} L^0 \leq e^{-\eta\Delta t(n+1)} L^0 = e^{-\eta t_{n+1}} L^0, \\ n &= 0, \dots, N-1. \end{aligned}$$

Let us denote

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &= \min_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq n \\ 0 \leq j \leq M-1}} \{ \sigma_{ij} : |\mu_j - \sigma_{ij}\mathbf{E}| = 0 \}, \\ 2 &= \max_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq n \\ 0 \leq j \leq M-1}} \{ \sigma_{ij} : |\mu_j - \sigma_{ij}\mathbf{E}| = 0 \}. \end{aligned}$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} 1\mathbf{E} &\leq \mu_j \leq 2\mathbf{E}, \\ j &= 0, \dots, M-1. \end{aligned}$$

Series Solution and Exact Result

$$\Delta x \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} (U_j^n, U_j^n) \leq L^n \leq C_2 e^{-\eta t_n} \Delta x \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} (U_j^0, U_j^0),$$

$$n = 0, \dots, N.$$

$$\Delta x \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} (U_j^n, U_j^n) \leq e^{-\eta t_n} \Delta x \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} (U_j^0, U_j^0),$$

$$n = 0, \dots, N; = 2/C_1.$$

Therefore, the numerical solution U_j^n of the mixed problem is exponentially stable in L_2 the norm.

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